

SHORT COMMUNICATION

Copper (II) Heterochelates*

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The 3d⁹ copper(II) complexes are subject to a considerable Jahn-Teller effect resulting mostly in distorted octahedral or distorted tetrahedral structures¹. The rose-red copper(II) bis-biguanide chloride is one of the very few exceptions, giving a square planar stereochemistry. We wondered if partial replacement of the biguanides by other strong field ligands would also lead to a square planar structure or give rise to distorted octahedral structure.

The heterochelates [Cu(*o*-phen) (BigH)]X₂ and [Cu(dipy) (BigH)] X₂ (*o*-phen=*o*-phenanthroline, dipy= α α' -dipyridyl, BigH=biguanide, X=Cl, Br or I) have been synthesised following two different approaches: (a) by feeding the blue monobiguanide copper (II) with *o*-phenanthroline or α α' -dipyridyl at pH 6.0 and (b) by feeding the μ -diol bis-*o*-phenanthroline (dipyridyl) dicopper ion by biguanide at pH 6.0–7.0. The colour of the complexes are influenced by the anion in the solid crystalline state (chloride, royal blue and the iodide blue black). The aqueous solution spectra provide asymmetric bands around a frequency, which is lower than an expected band in a square planar complex and much higher than what would be expected for a tetrahedral stereochemistry. The magnetic moments (1.8 B.M.) also stand against a tetrahedral structure, which should have considerable orbital contribution. The iodide salt dissolves in water and also in methanol, providing different spectral characteristics, which behaviour favours a distorted octahedral structure^{2,3}.

Besides the above complexes a number of other heterochelates with substituted biguanides (methyl biguanide=MeBigH and ethyl-biguanide) and the substituted 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthrolins have also been synthesised and characterised.

A series of mixed chelates, using *o*-phenanthroline (or α α' dipyridyl) and glycine (or α -alanine) have also been prepared and characterised. Aqueous solution spectra as also room temperature magnetic moment indicate a distorted octahedral complex.

This has also been possible to synthesize a number of copper(II) heterochelates with a tridentate, dibasic Schiff's base (say, salicylaldehyde—anthranilic acid, ('SAH₂') and a molecule of *o*-phenanthroline or α α' dipyridyl. The alcoholic spectra of these complexes are significantly different from most of the foregoing chelates. These provide three distinct bands, the longest wavelength band being still higher in energy than what has been observed in several copper (II) Schiff's base complexes having a distorted tetrahedral

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1. Ballhausen, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw Hill, New York, 1962, p. 268.
2. Forster and Goodgame, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2796.
3. Goodgame and Haines, *ibid.*, 1966, Section A, 175.

structure⁴. A blue crystalline non-electrolyte complex [Cu (dipy)(IDA)] (where IDA_n = iminodiacetic acid) has also been characterised.

The analyses, spectral characteristics and magnetic moments of eleven Copper(II)-hetero chelates are given in the table.

TABLE
Spectral character and Magnetic moment of Copper(II) Heterochelates

Complex	Analytical Results				Colour	Absorption Spectral Bands		Magnetic Moment B.M.
	%Cu	%N	%Cl/Br/I	%H ₂ O*		Wave number ν , (cm ⁻¹)		
1. [Cu(<i>o</i> -phen) (BigH)] Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Found: 13.90 Reqd: 14.10	20.09 19.43	15.86 15.80	7.96 8.00	Royal blue	16940—15630 cm ⁻¹		1.80 B.M.
2. [Cu(<i>o</i> -phen) (BigH)] I ₂ ·H ₂ O	Found: 10.12 Reqd: 10.31	15.10 15.92	40.75 41.26	2.66 2.92	Blue black	(a) 16940—15630 (b) 22730—22220 (i) 15330—12820	—	—
3. [Cu (dipy) (BigH)] I ₂ ·H ₂ O	Found: 10.47 Reqd: 10.74	16.70 16.57	49.25 42.91	3.50 3.04	Blue black	(a) 16660—15630 (b) 23260—22730 (i) 13510—12820 (ii) 17240—16670	—	—
4. [Cu (nitrophen) (BigH)] Cl ₂ ·O.5H ₂ O	Found: — Reqd: —	23.53 23.88	15.08 15.13	2.33 1.92	Sky blue	(a) 16950—15380	1.82	—
5. [Cu (nitrophen) (Me BigH)] Cl ₂ ·O.5H ₂ O	Found: — Reqd: —	23.24 23.18	14.95 14.71	2.45 1.86	Blue black	(a) 16670—15380	—	—
6. [Cu (gly) (<i>o</i> -phen)] Cl ₂ ·3H ₂ O	Found: 15.40 Reqd: 15.56	10.68 10.29	8.65 8.70	13.70 13.23	Deep blue	(a) 16670—15630	1.83	—
7. [Cu (dipy) (α -alan)] Cl ₂ ·1.5H ₂ O	Found: 17.01 Reqd: 17.16	11.40 11.35	9.63 9.59	7.81 7.29	Deep blue	(a) 16940—15880	1.90	—
8. [Cu (dipy) (SA)] O.5H ₂ O	Found: 13.42 Reqd: 13.57	8.71 8.98	—	2.15 1.92	Olive green	(a) 26320—23810 (ii) 14490—13700 (iii) 12200—11900	1.86	—
9. [Cu (<i>o</i> -phen) (SA)]	Found: 12.80 Reqd: 13.14	8.72 8.69	—	0	Olive green	(a) 26320—23810 (ii) 14710—13700 (iii) 12200—11760	1.86	—
10. [Cu (dipy) (IDA)] 4.5H ₂ O	Found: 14.62 Reqd: 14.99	9.87 9.97	—	19.23 18.70	Blue		1.84	—
11. [Cu (dipy) (gly)] Cl ₂ ·1.5H ₂ O	Found: 17.44 Reqd: 17.89	11.44 11.76	9.67 9.92	8.32 7.56	Deep blue	(a) 16940—15880	1.90	—

* By loss at 110°

'a' means aqueous solution, 'b' methanol and 's' ethanol solution.

4. Sacconi and Ciampolini, *ibid.*, 1964, 276.

Extensive spectral measurements in solution have been completed on the composition and formation of most of the foregoing mixed chelate systems.

Our completed studies on the synthesis, visible absorption spectra (both solution and diffuse reflectance), magnetic moments, stereochemistry, and properties of the Cu(II)-hetero-complexes will appear in due course. We also plan to undertake further studies on the heterochelates [Cu(gly) (BigH) X] and [Cu (alan) BigH]X (glyH=glycine, alanH=(α)-alanine and X=Cl,Br,I) reported many years ago⁵.

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